

Effects Of Dentifrices On Surface Properties Of Cad - Cam Manufactured Temporary Restorative Materials

Research Article

N.E Kaviya¹, Karthickraj S.M^{2*}

¹Student, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences (SIMATS), Saveetha University, Chennai- 77, India.

²Senior Lecturer, Department of Periodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences [SIMATS], Saveetha University, Chennai- 77, India.

Abstract

Aim: The aim of the study is to find the effects of dentifrices on surface properties of Computer-aided design and computer-aided manufacturing (CAD-CAM) temporary restorative materials.

Materials and Methods: 12 printed Poly methyl methacrylate (PMMA) blocks were collected from the CAD-CAM centre. Blocks were mounted on the die stone and 4 types of dentifrices were used for the novel technique in this study. The preparation surface roughness was taken using a stylus profilometer then the blocks were placed in the brushing stimulator (Tooth-brush stimulator ZM3.8) and readings were taken again after cycles for 1 month and 3 months.

Results and Discussion: Results show that there is no significant difference in the surface roughness of the PMMA blocks before and after brushing with different dentifrices for 1 month and 3 months cycles. Anova values show no significance among the Roughness average (Ra), Root mean square roughness (Rq) and arithmetic mean value of the single roughness depths of consecutive sampling length (Rz) values of preoperative, 1 month and 3 months.

Conclusion: The study concludes that different dentifrices have no significant changes in the surface properties of the CAD-CAM manufactured PMMA blocks.

Keywords: Dentifrices; Computer-Aided Design and Computer-Aided Manufacturing (CAD/CAM); Poly Methyl Methacrylate (PMMA); Surface Properties; Novel Technique.

Introduction

A restoration that is used as a temporary or a permanent solution should have a good abrasive resistance [1]. Abrasive wear occurs mainly during the process of mastication and cleaning the tooth mechanically using toothbrushes, maintaining poor dental hygiene and decreased saliva production may lead to high plaque accumulation and cause stomatitis and oral candidiasis [2]. Tooth brushing is one of the common causes for the abrasion of the tooth surface and the restorative materials due to the mechanical process of mastication in the occlusal surface. The tooth brushing affects the roughness measurements and the gloss of the restorative material [3]. Many studies show that the stimulation of the brushing leads to the decrease in the life span of the restora-

tive materials as they produce changes in the surface properties of the restorative material [4].

A wide integration of computer aided design (CAD) and computer aided manufacturing (CAM) in dentistry, an increasingly large number of novel technical and clinical protocols have been introduced for provisional restorations manufacturing in a digital workflow [5]. The CAD-CAM aided monolithic materials are preferred as they reduce the time of manufacturing and decrease the number of appointments [6]. The need for polishing any CAD-CAM manufactured restorative materials is to eliminate the surface defects caused by the machine and to reduce the surface roughness on the external surface of the restorative material [7].

Restoration in the field of dentistry is very important and on a

*Corresponding Author:

Dr Karthickraj S.M,

Senior Lecturer, Department of Periodontics, Saveetha Dental College and Hospitals, Saveetha Institute of Medical and Technical Sciences [SIMATS], Saveetha University, Chennai 600 077, Tamil Nadu, India.

Tel: 9840094540

E-mail: karthickrajasm.sdc@saveetha.com

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base for the permanent restoration or solution there is a need for temporary restorations. Restoration materials on their chemical composition can be divided into monomethacrylate or acrylic resins, which include polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) and poly ethyl/butyl methacrylate (PEMA) [8]. (PMMA) Polymethylmethacrylate is an amorphous thermoplastic which is derived from methylmethacrylate by the process of addition polymerization. This material has many purposes and serves good for restoration but has poor scratch resistance [9]. PMMA is preferred in the restorative field for its lightweight, transparency, low cost [10] and they even produce low oxidative stress which reduces the incidence of periodontitis. PMMA has also shown its side effects like COVID-19 on the cardiovascular system by inducing hypotension and bradycardia. A wide variety of pre-polymerised polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) blocks have been introduced on the market based on further studies related with nanoparticles and data was produced on surface roughness [11]. Our team has extensive knowledge and research experience that has translated into high quality publications [12-24, 25-31].

The aim of this study was to find the effects of dentifrices on surface properties of CAD-CAM temporary restorative materials which are the PMMA blocks.

Materials and Methods

12 printed PMMA blocks were collected from the CAD-CAM centre. Blocks were mounted on the die stone and 4 types of dentifrices were used for the study. The surface roughness was calculated pre and post brushing using a stylus profilometer. The

Ra, Rq and Rz values were calculated. Ra-Roughness average, Rq-Root mean square roughness, Rz- The arithmetic mean value of the single roughness depths of consecutive sampling lengths. The surface roughness readings before the stimulation was taken then the blocks were placed in the brushing stimulator -Toothbrush stimulator ZM3.8. A total of 2500 cycles were done from which for 1 month 834 cycles were done in linear motion. 1666 cycles were done from 3 months stimulation which includes 833 linear motion and 833 as clockwise 433 cycles and anti-clockwise 400 cycles. Readings of the Ra, Rq and Rz values were taken after cycles for 1 month and 3 months using a stylus profilometer and the readings were recorded accordingly for obtaining the results and graphs.

Results and Discussion

Results show that there is no significant difference in the surface roughness of the PMMA blocks before and after brushing with different dentifrices for 1 month and 3 months cycles. At 1 month, 1 and At 3rd month, 0.441. The Ra mean p value shows preoperative, 0.16; At 1 month, 1 and At 3rd month, 0.441 shown in graph 1. The Rq mean p value shows preoperative, 0.441; At 1 month, 0.33 and At 3rd month, 0.33 shown in graph 2. The Rz mean p value shows preoperative, 2.437; At 1 month, 1.245 and At 3rd month, 2.014 shown in graph 3. that the Anova values show no significance among the Ra, Rq and Rz values of preoperative, 1 month and 3 months and the P value also no significant difference in the Ra, Rq and Rz values of the preoperative, 1 month and 3 months. These results showed that there is no significant difference on the PMMA blocks based on the type of dentifrices

Figure1. Shows the brushes and the toothpaste used for the study.

Figure 2. Shows the Stylus profilometer that was used for analysing the surface property of the restorative material.

Figure 3. Shows the Brushing stimulator-Toothbrush stimulator ZM3.8 that was used for stimulating the brushing techniques on the restorative material.

Table 1. Represents the mean values of the Ra, Rq and Rz values of the different types of dentifrices.

Dentifrices	RaPre	Ra1Mo	Ra3Mo	RqPre	Rq1Mo	Rq3Mo	RzPre	Rz1Mo	Rz3Mo
Dabur red	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.006	0.064	0.043
Meswak	0.005	0.005	0.004	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.072	0.065	0.042
Sensodyne	0.006	0.005	0.004	0.008	0.006	0.005	0.074	0.07	0.052
Colgate	0.006	0.005	0.004	0.007	0.006	0.005	0.071	0.008	0.032

Figure 4. Shows the mean Ra values preoperative in which X the axis represents the type of dentifrices and the Y axis represents the test value. At 1st month and At 3rd month. Anova values Ra Pre-2.25 and 1 month-1. P values Ra Pre-0.16 and Ra 1 month-0.441. (Ra Pre p value - 0.16; $p > 0.05$) and (Ra 1 month p value - 0.441; $p > 0.05$) Hence the changes in Ra value did not differ significantly as the p value was not statistically significant.

Figure 5. Shows the mean Rq values preoperative in which the X axis represents the type of dentifrices and Y the axis represents the test value. 1st month and At 3rd month. Anova values Rq Pre-1, 1 month-1.333 and 3 months-1.333. P value RqPre-0.441, 1 month-0.33 and 3 months-0.33. (Rq Pre p value - 0.441; $p > 0.05$), (Rq 1 month p value - 0.33; $p > 0.05$) and (Rq 3 month p value - 0.33; $p > 0.05$) Hence the changes in Rq value did not differ significantly as the p value was not statistically significant.

Figure 6. Shows the mean Rz values preoperative in which the X axis represents the type of dentifrices and the Y axis represents the test value. 1st month and At 3rd month. Anova values RzPre-2.437, 1 month-1.245 and 3 months-2.014. P value RzPre-0.136, 1 month-0.356 and 3 months-0.191. P(RzPre p value - 0.136; $p > 0.05$), (Rz 1 month p value - 0.356; $p > 0.05$) and (Rz 3 month p value - 0.191; $p > 0.05$) Hence the changes in Rz value did not differ significantly as the p value was not statistically significant.

used on analysing the surface roughness for about three months before and after the mechanical process of brushing.

The PMMA blocks used in the study did not have any significance of changes in the preoperative, 1 month and 3rd month surface properties. Previous studies show that surface properties of monolithic CAD/CAM restorative materials were differently affected by the abrasive toothbrushing and storage media [32]. The surface roughness values of all tested materials were below

the plaque accumulation threshold [33]. The provisional materials prepared in the CAD/CAM have better mechanical properties for the clinical application compared to conventional materials [34].

Conclusion

Under the limitation of the study, it can be concluded that different types of dentifrices had no significant changes in the surface properties of the CAD-CAM manufactured PMMA blocks.

There is a need for larger study sample to get a better understanding of these properties in further studies.

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